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Engineering grand challenges and the attributes of the global engineer: a literature review

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ABSTRACT

Technology has been changing world in ways never imagined. The ever-evolving society and rapid development posed different demands and challenges to the engineering profession. Addressing these challenges means to re-vision and reform the ways we educate future engineers and the attributes need to be enhanced. This paper reports a literature review with aim to (1) understand the different stakeholders' perspectives, namely students, educators, and employers, (2) understand the profile of the global engineer (i.e. knowledge, competences and skills), and (3) outline and discuss learning strategies. As a result, the paper presents the main gaps in the existing knowledge, formulates research hypothesis, and proposes a research design for a follow up empirical study to investigate further the engineering grand challenges, the attributes needed to solve them, and the learning environments required.

Conference Key Areas: Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Engineering education, grand challenges, attributes, learning strategies

INTRODUCTION

In the past decades, international reports and research have outlined the central role technology plays in the contemporary society and the global challenges being faced. Engineering education always evolves and adapts to social challenges. In the past, engineering education reacted to social challenges by adding disciplines to the curriculum. In the present, engineering education must take a proactive response to the current fast societal change [1], [2]. For example, the UNESCO report on "Engineering: Issues, Challenges and Opportunities for development" [2, p. 6] looks into the global context in which engineers operate and the need to "effectively innovate and apply engineering and technology to global issues and challenges such as poverty reduction, sustainable development, and climate change – and urgently develop greener engineering and lower carbon technology". The National Academy of Engineering [1], [3] also examines the roles engineers will play and the professional contexts of the future, pointing to aspirations and desired attributes. Professional contexts include systems perspectives, customerization, public policy debates, and understanding of engineering, calling for attributes related to systems thinking, teamwork, communication, interdisciplinary knowledge, creativity, and innovation. The Global Engineering Deans Council [4], in cooperation with the International Federation of Engineering Education Societies (IFEES), launched a survey to validate the performance and proficiency of the competencies defined in the last years by international engineering organisations and which are considered essential for the preparation, performance, and employability of future engineers. From this study, five broad categories emerged: technical, professional, personal, interpersonal, and cross-cultural competences [4] which define the "Attributes of a Global Engineer". These reports do not only point towards engineering education challenges and the requirements to address them, they also refer to the critical gap between what needs to be taught and what is taught in engineering schools. However, it is up to the institution, academic staff, and students to construct and develop a curriculum and learning environment that enhances the "global engineer" attributes.

This paper reports a literature review with aim to (1) understand the different stakeholders' perspectives, namely students, educators, and employers, (2) understand the profile of the global engineer (i.e. knowledge, competences, and skills), and (3) outline and discuss learning strategies. As a result, the paper presents the main gaps in the existing knowledge, formulates research hypothesis, and proposes a research design for a follow up empirical study to investigate further the engineering grand challenges, the attributes needed to solve them, and the learning environments required.

Using thematic keywords such as “engineering education challenges”, “engineering education students' perspectives”, “engineering education industry perspectives”, etc. relevant literature was searched. Different bibliographic databases and engineering education journals were used. In this paper, we focus mainly on research articles and books. The following three sections address the different themes referred to in the above aims.

1 STUDENTS' AND INDUSTRY PERSPECTIVES ON ENGINEERING EDUCATION

Studies, concept position papers, and reviews involving engineering education stakeholders, namely students, academic staff and industry, are not new in the literature (see for example [5]–[9]). These publications explore different themes and provide valuable knowledge to develop and innovate engineering education further. Curriculum reforms, preparedness for professional life, type of attributes are examples of the themes explored (see for example [10], [11]).

Several empirical studies focus on investigating curriculum reforms and use students' grades and ratings to validate the changes implemented. They show efforts, mainly at course and programme levels, in changing engineering education and are built on the need to develop the right skills for the professional practice (see for example [12]–[14]). Some studies explore students' perspectives about their qualification and preparedness for professional life using surveys and interviews as methods (see for example [5]–[7]). This paper focuses on the latter literature in order to investigate industry and students' perspective on engineering education and preparation for the profession. The publications addressing specifically industry perspectives involve mainly literature reviews and position papers [5], [8], [15]. They do not focus so much on what kind of learning pedagogies but give hints of features learning environments should recreate. On the other hand, it seems that there is a lack of studies taking the academic staff perspectives on these themes. Independently of the type of stakeholder, all publications point to how engineers should be educated, their professional roles and contexts, as well as the attributes needed to thrive. They also provide insights to the discourses and interpretations the different groups of stakeholders have about skills needed and their enhancement.

McMasters [8], [15] refers to the engineering profession as an “*ever-evolving*”, “*ever-volatile*” and “*ever-changing*” enterprise, which is a response to society's demands. Consequently, there is a need for close collaboration between governments, industry and academe in order to: (1) define and discuss the needed steps to supply well-prepared graduates with (2) the right skills and motivation to thrive in an engineering career. These include a reflection on how to attract and retain engineering students and how they are being educated. Focusing on the latter, the author uses the evolution of aerospace engineering, the professional environment and demands (namely

market, environment and social demands) to present the 21st century engineer and the type and scope of the attributes needed.

Presently, one of the major developments in engineering professions is the invention of *integrated product teams* (IPT) and *integrated product development* (IPD)², where processes of design, manufacturing and marketing are integrated by bringing together interdisciplinary groups (including customers) [5], [8], [16]–[18]. This leads, for example, to a re-conceptualization of teamwork and systems thinking as attributes, namely in what kind of teams students form, what kind of problems and contexts they learn from and the subsequent skills enhanced (e.g. creative and critical thinking, problem solving, self-directed learning, etc.) [5], [6], [8]. Other attributes are creativity and innovation that are primary requirements for rapid technological breakthroughs [8].

Almi *et al.* [6] refers to rapid advancement of software engineering and the gap between engineering education and industry requirements. The latter consider that young engineers are not ready to face “real life” due to a highly demanding environment where it is required for graduates to work under pressure, have good communication skills, and be able to follow processes, have a solid work ethic, and project management skills.

In sum, there are few studies investigating the industry and employers perspectives about attributes.

The emphasis is not only on the set of attributes needed, but also on how they intertwine and the formats assumed in connection to professional practice (i.e. breadth and depth). From the industry perspective, two type of attributes are emphasised: teamwork and (design) system thinking.

Martin *et al.* [5] investigates engineering graduates perspectives of how well they were prepared for work in industry. The results show that students perceived their strengths in technical background, problem solving, formal communication and life-long learning attributes. The study also identifies weaknesses areas, which are: work in multi-disciplinary teams, leadership, practical preparation and management skills. Similarly, to the industry perspective, teamwork appears as an important attribute and it is presented along with good interpersonal skills (e.g. listening skills, sharing information, cooperation with office colleagues, and cope with office dynamics) and leadership. Furthermore, teamwork is discussed from two perspectives: horizontal (e.g. teams formed by different engineering experts) and vertical (e.g. collaboration with different levels within company).

Another attribute pointed to is lifelong learning which is defined as the ability to *adapt to changing work environments, learn new skills, and assess one’s own abilities* [5, p. 169]. Once more, this attribute is very much aligned with the industry perspective and the current vision of the engineering profession, i.e. ever-volatile enterprise.

Hasse *et al.* [7] defined four types of engineer groups based on students perceived relevance of technical skills (e.g. science and mathematics) and non-technical skills (e.g. interpersonal and professional skills). The four groups vary from (i) high focus on technical skills, (ii) high focus on both technical and non-technical skills, (iii) high focus on non-technical skills. The groups profile depended on different factors, namely gender, confidence, and motivation for the engineering profession. Furthermore, this study shows the heterogeneity among engineering students and the propensity of the

² See for example the Principles of Integrated Product Development at <http://www.npd-solutions.com/>

at risk group to drop out. Therefore, it is important to consider the curriculum and learning experiences provided to engineering students in order to attract, retain, and motivate them. In the professional setting, engineers assume different and complex roles and work in multidisciplinary teams; consequently, the way students are educated should not only mimic these conditions but also provide possibilities for students to create their “portfolio of attributes”. Streiner *et al.* [19] refers to relevance of multicultural and international learning experiences as a means to prepare students to a globalized profession.

In summary, the literature refers to reasons it is needed to qualify engineers with attributes beyond the technical ones. From the perspectives considered, literature shows an overlap on the types of attributes needed (i.e. breadth) and their different landscapes of practice (i.e. depth). Consequently, educating engineers for the 21st century is not only about equipping students with adequate attributes but also takes into consideration the heterogeneity of motivations and exposing them to a diversity of learning experiences which enhance the needed attributes and mimic the professional practice. To achieve this, it is important how academia collaborates with industry and the surrounding communities. Another interesting point worth referring to is that most references and studies cited refer to Australia, US and European contexts. There is a lacking perspective from Asian and African contexts and engineering challenges.

2 PROFILE OF THE GLOBAL ENGINEER

The profile of a global engineer consists of the attributes necessary for the engineer to successfully interweave the technical, business, human, cultural, and environmental aspects of society’s problems to bring forth solutions for grand challenges. This literature review seeks to identify and validate those attributes. A comprehensive work was completed by the Global Engineers Deans Council (GEDC) [4] to create a list of attributes. Following is a description of the list and perspectives brought from a variety of recent works to both confirm the list and identify any aspects of the list that might need further expansion.

The *Attributes of a Global Engineer Project* is the work of the International Engineering Education special interest group, a sub-group of the American Society of Engineering Education’s (ASEE) corporate membership council. This group, in coordination with the GEDC, the International Federation of Engineering Education Societies (IFEES), and supported by the Boeing Company, developed and validated a list of the “desired competencies and characteristics needed by engineers to effectively live, work, and perform in a global context [20].” We use these attributes as the point of departure for this study. The attributes, now commonly associated with the GEDC are paraphrased in table 1. Validation starts with comparing the attributes to the expectations of engineering outcomes. Two such expectations are the graduate attributes of the Washington Accord [21] and the ABET student learning outcomes [22]. All of these attributes and outcomes are accounted for in the GEDC attributes of the global engineer.

Table 1. Attributes of Global Engineer

• Technical	Think individually and cooperatively
Fundamental principle understanding	Positive self image and confidence
Technical literacy	Initiative and willingness to learn
Product life-cycle	• Interpersonal

Project management	Functions on team
• Professional	Mentors others
Communicate in variety of ways	• Cross-cultural
Communicate to tech and non-tech audiences	Political, social, economic perspectives
High professional competence	Applies business and ethical norms in context
Continuous improvement	Global perspective
Effective decision making	Language fluency
• Personal	Interdisciplinary perspective
Think creatively and critically	

In 2004, the National Academy of Engineering (NAE) [1] published the attributes of engineers in 2020 as a forward-looking vision on needs of the practicing engineer. Now, as 2020 is approaching, the vision provides grounding to the new work of the GEDC. The paraphrased list from the Engineer 2020 includes: strong analytical skills, practical ingenuity, creativity, communication, business and management, leadership, high ethical standards, professionalism, dynamism, agility, resilience, flexibility, and lifelong learning [1]. Of this list, most items are explicitly presented in the attributes of the global engineer, however, leadership, practical ingenuity and dynamism, agility, resilience, and flexibility are not explicit.

While not stated in the GEDC attributes list, the comprehensive list would align with the skills commonly associated with effective leadership such as communication, professional competence, effective decision making, positive self-image, etc. With regards to practical ingenuity, the NAE describes ingenuity as “skill in planning, combining, and adapting... to solve problems” [1]. This concept could be derived from the GEDC attributes, but perhaps is important enough to be explicitly stated when considering the grand challenges.

Thomas Friedman in *Thank you for Being Late* [23], identifies how, for the first time in history, the advances in technology (due to rapid growth in computer speeds, data storage, software, and sensing capabilities) are outpacing the abilities of humans to adapt to change. This phenomenon highlights the need for engineers to possess the attributes of dynamism, agility, resilience, and flexibility in order to quickly adapt to problems and find solutions in new contexts.

We believe that the concepts of practical ingenuity and dynamism, agility, resiliency, and flexibility should be made explicit when addressing the grand challenges as opposed to being implicit as combinations of the GEDC global attributes.

In *Educating Engineers* in 2009 [24], Sheri Sheppard *et al.* describe the need to majorly transform engineering education to better align with the needs of engineering practice. Sheppard *et al.* contend that the new-century engineer must have the attributes presented by the NAE in Engineer 2020 and also be focused on the professional values as described in the many codes of conduct published by professional society. In particular, these values are being competent in one’s own work, not misrepresenting one’s own competences, and continuing to build one’s own competence [24]. The

competences themselves are quite well presented by the GEDC global attributes; however, Sheppard's *et al.* work brings to light the need for the engineer to explicitly "own" these competences through a self-analysis of strengths, weaknesses, and continuous improvement. This explicit identity of one's self as an engineer would fall into the "personal category" of the GEDC attributes and is one that we see as essential for an engineer to be able to develop.

Al-Atabi, a member of the GEDC, wrote a handbook for Conceive, Design, Implement, and Operate (CDIO³) implementation, *Think Like an Engineer* [25]. Beyond the CDIO explanations, Al-Atabi includes a chapter on emotional intelligence. Self-awareness, social awareness, empathy, and relationship management are addressed in this chapter. These attributes lead the engineer to be able to understand equity and empower inclusivity. The 2014 comprehensive *Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research* [26] dedicates a complete section to diversity and inclusiveness. In many parts of the world, the engineering profession suffers from a lack of diversity. Inclusivity emerges as a necessary attribute for the global engineers to both navigate relationships within the profession and to understand the contexts for problem solutions.

In the *Making of an Expert Engineer* [27], James Trevelyan interviewed and observed practicing engineers to distinguish the patterns associated with engineers who were well regarded to be "exceptional performers". Synthesized results identify attributes associated with successful practice. The foundations he identified are: engineering and business science, tacit ingenuity, and accurate perception skills. Further pointed out is the "extent to which engineering practice relies on human performances, particularly collaborative performances" [27]. Through a comprehensive analysis and description, Trevelyan both validates the majority of attributes put forth in the GEDC global list and brings further light to the issues of self-awareness and environmental sustainability. As was brought to light by *Engineer 2020*, the concept of ingenuity as an explicit attribute is further verified as well.

Looking to the future of engineering education, Goldberg and Somerville published *A Whole New Engineer: The Coming Revolution in Engineering Education* [28]. The authors categorize the aspects of an engineer in a way substantially different than the lists of attributes put forth by the other sources in the literature. They identify the engineer has having six minds. They are: 1) analytical mind, 2) design mind, 3) linguistic mind, 4) people mind, 5) body mind, and 6) mindful mind. The global attributes from GEDC could be associated with each of these minds. However, some of these "minds" receive little attention in the global attributes. In particular, the people mind and the mindful mind address the need to understand one's self and others and how these human connections evolve into the improvements engineers make for society. Additionally, the mindful mind expands the global attribute of "willingness to learn" to include the ability to reflect and direct one's own learning [28]. This expands the idea of lifelong learning to a more comprehensive model of self-directed learning [29].

The perspectives of the GEDC came from the perspectives of corporate members and academic leaders. They received inspiration from the *NAE Engineer 2020* [1], but in retrospect we reached back to that publication to identify the importance of ideas not

³ CDIO is a framework intended to educate the upcoming generations of engineers. The CDIO syllabus uses four areas to identify the development of engineers: 1) disciplinary knowledge and reasoning, 2) personal and professional skills and attributes, 3) interpersonal skills: teamwork and communication, 4) conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating systems in the enterprise, societal and environmental context [37].

explicitly stated in the GEDC list. Sheppard addressed the perspective of designing engineering education and highlighted the attributes needed to meet the professional societies' codes. Trevelyan took the perspective of expertise in practice. Goldberg and Somerville were looking at a coming revolution in engineering education and how the whole new engineer will be developed. From the wide variety of perspectives in this literature, we are able to find complete validation of the global engineer attributes list. Further we found evidence that there are parts of the list that need expansion in order for the global engineer to face the grand challenges. The modified list is included below with additions underlined.

Technical: Engineering-related knowledge, skills, and abilities needed for success

- Demonstrates an understanding of engineering, science, and mathematics fundamentals
- Demonstrates an understanding of information technology, digital competency, information literacy, and systems thinking
- Demonstrates an understanding of stages/phases of product lifecycle (design, prototyping, testing, production, distribution channels, supplier management, etc.)
- Demonstrates an understanding of project planning, management, and the impacts of projects on various stakeholder groups (project team members, project sponsor, project client, end users, etc.)
- Applies practical ingenuity to the solution of complex problems

Professional: Workplace related competencies for global performance

- Communicates effectively in a variety of different ways, methods, and media (written, verbal/oral, graphic, listening, electronically, etc.)
- Communicates effectively to both technical and non-technical audiences
- Maintains a high-level of professional competence
- Embraces a commitment to quality principles/standards and continuous improvement
- Applies personal and professional judgment in effectively making decisions and managing risks

Personal: Individual characteristics needed for global flexibility

- Possesses the ability to think both critically and creatively
- Possesses the ability to think both individually and cooperatively
- Maintains a positive self-image and possesses positive self-confidence
- Possesses a self-awareness and capability to identify one's own strengths and weaknesses in order to manage continuous personal development
- Shows initiative and demonstrates a willingness, and capability to learn self-directedly
- Demonstrates perseverance, urgency, resourcefulness, and flexibility

Interpersonal: Skills and perspectives to work on interdependent global teams

- Functions effectively on a team (understands team goals, contributes effectively to team work, supports team decisions, respects team members, etc.)
- Mentors or helps others accomplish goals/tasks
- Acts inclusively and equitably

Cross-cultural: Society and cultural understanding to embrace diverse viewpoints

- Demonstrates an understanding of political, social, economic, and environmental/sustainability perspectives

- Demonstrates an understanding of the ethical and business norms and applies norms effectively in a given context (organization, industry, country, etc.)
- Possesses an international/global perspective
- Possesses fluency in at least two languages
- Embraces an interdisciplinary/multidisciplinary perspective

Figure 1. Profile of the global engineer – modified from GEDC global engineer project

3 LEARNING STRATEGIES AND GOOD PRACTICE EXAMPLES

Clearly, twenty first engineering graduates must be skilled in competencies beyond the traditional technical competencies of the engineering profession [20]. Engineering education must be comprised of three key axes: technical, professional, and global skills [30]. This section will look at what are the learning principles to develop the needed attributes, what are good curricular examples, and how are they organized.

The engineering education system of the future will need to be broad-based to provide the needed flexibility and adaptability for the every changing technology and environment. At the same time, the current gap needs to be addressed between what needs to be taught and what is taught in engineering schools.

Goldberg & Sommerville, in *A Whole New Engineer: The Coming Revolution in Engineering Education* [28], provide three important historical transformation lessons: 1) changes cannot be small, minor tweaks to curriculum do not work; 2) students are sensitive how genuine the education system is to the work world; and 3) approaches and strategies of change from the past have failed to bring about desired change. This has resulted in engineering education being severely misaligned with the times.

While there may be a developing broad agreement within the engineering community that a need exists to better prepare engineers for global practice [31], there is less agreement as to what educational experiences will be best develop the desired attributes in graduates and even more so in terms of the means and metrics to judge it.

The GEDC identified the following curricular considerations or learning principles for developing the competencies for twenty first century graduates:

- Experience in an increasingly distributed team context, which crosses country and cultural boundaries.
- Promote awareness of the broader impacts of engineering
- Broader perspective than is available in many current curricula
- institutions need to assess their curriculum in its ability to meet needs
- Need for industry involvement
- Recent trend in engineering education involving project-based courses, especially with projects overseas

They also recognize that “it is up to the institution, academic staff, and students to construct and develop a curriculum and learning environment that enhances the ‘global engineer’ attributes” [20].

A review of engineering literature readily support for each of the curricular considerations. Trevelyan [27] in *The Making of an Expert Engineer* identifies one of the issues with current engineering curriculum is that few, if any, engineering education have extensive engineering practice (beyond laboratory research). More need to

consider professional practice experiences such as the project-based consideration identified by GEDC. Trevelyan also identifies issues with rewarding individual achievements versus rewarding results through working with others, reinforcing the need for more curricular time focused on working in a team context that closely reflect the professional work environment.

Al-Atabi [25] identifies with the second and third considerations by calling for a focus on system level thinking and application to education along through a team learning experience utilizing real projects and holistic learning. Grasso and Martinelli [32] also identify the need for engineers to practice more holistic thinking and avoid the prevalent and needless limitation of solution spaces to only those that contain technological answers while sorely lacking consideration for the many other contextual factors involved with actual engineering professional practice.

Sheppard, *et al.* [24], in *Educating Engineers: Designing for the Future of the Field*, emphasis the need to engage practitioners to bring professional practice to the center of the student engineering education expertise. They state that “curriculum changes focused on introducing educational experiences to develop attitudes and skills in concert with disciplinary-oriented scientific and technical knowledge are difficult to effect”. Faculty must work in an interactive fashion, just like practicing engineers, to create academic programming that is better aligned with professional practice across the entire student curriculum and within individual courses, “by reflecting, assessing, debating, designing, and prototyping a truly networked undergraduate engineering program, one that engages both the teacher and student in learning in the context of professional design”.

Educating the Engineer of 2020 [3] provides a similar guiding strategy for curriculum improvement and proposes that effective improvements for engineering education must focus on the whole educational system and move beyond the current ineffective approach of incremental improvements to single aspects of complex curriculums. The publication also promotes a systems level educational change.

What are some good education examples based on these learning processes? How is the curriculum organized? The 2012 Graham report [33] and the 2010 and 2013 UNESCO reports [2], [34] identify problem/project-based learning (PBL) as an integral part of successful curricular changes and as one of the key steps in the “design and implementation of an effective engineering curriculum,” respectfully. Graham’s study revealed that a majority of the highly regarded examples of change involved the use of PBL within an “authentic, professional engineering context.” Project-based learning is a core theme throughout the 2013 UNESCO report to achieve the Washington Accord graduate attributes and to provide the “personal learning experiences” needed for the transformation of engineering education. It identifies that,

“Project Based Learning (PBL) is a widely reported approach to address the need to change engineering education, from the formal presentation of technical material to a student experience model. It provides activities, which simulate the role and responsibilities of practicing engineers, and develops the general graduate attributes that have been identified as essential. [...] This relates more closely to a realistic engineering environment, provides an opportunity for students to learn from each other, and assists the development of the essential graduate attributes of team- work and leadership.”

The Cambridge Handbook of Engineering Education Research [26] also positions PBL as an educational practice worth consideration. The second section of the handbook,

“Engineering Learning Mechanisms and Approaches,” focuses on approaches for transitioning from traditional to a variety of active student learning approaches in engineering education. This section begins with an explanation of problem-based and project-based learning models by Kolmos and de Graaff as an example of the curricular approaches engineering education should be considering [35].

Some good examples of PBL were part of a 2014-2015 a series, entitled PBL History and Diversity, broadcasted from the UNESCO Center for PBL at Aalborg University. The series has been captured in a soon to be published book, *PBL in Engineering Education: International Perspectives on Curricular Change* [11]. The book begins with defining PBL and providing a historic perspective of PBL. It is based on the 40+ years of PBL at Aalborg University and then continues with six additional models and practices of PBL implementation at higher education institutions across the world.

Connecting these PBL models back to the learning principles identified by the GEDC, they all:

- Have an integrative approach that utilize a team-based approach
- Through the real-life context of the work, promote awareness of the broader impacts of engineering and also develops the broader perspective for students
- Due to the professional practice nature of the experiences, industry or real-life customers/projects are needed. Student performance on these project provides some assessment on the curriculum’s ability to meet desired educational needs
- Certainly incorporates the use of project-based courses

Not only do these examples represent the potential for PBL to develop the attributes of a global engineer, the global application represented addresses a critique for the tendency towards only North American or European perspectives for the global approaches and impacts of engineering [36]; clearly from these examples, PBL represents the cultural perspectives from around the globe. If attributes desired are those of a global engineer, any approaches to improvement of engineering education must fit into all the cultures of the world.

4 MAIN CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a literature review regarding the attributes needed to address engineering global challenges. It starts by looking into students and industry perspectives where the evolution of professional practice aligned with society change and technological development emphasise the attributes needed such as multi- and interdisciplinary teamwork and systems thinking. The literature review not only define and validate, in detail, the breadth and depth of these attributes but also refers to the type of learning environment and experiences needed. The learning environment and experiences emphasise students’ active role and participation in the learning process and curriculum constructions like problem based, project organised learning (PBL) advocate. Even though curricular transformations and research about the ways 21st century engineers are educated have been addressed in the engineering education community, there are some remaining questions namely: (1) Are the curriculum changes sufficient to address the societal challenges and produce engineers with right qualifications? (2) How are the attributes defined as learning outcomes and enhanced (in both breadth and depth) in curricular changes? (3) How do the different stakeholders define and prioritize the attributes listed? (4) How well do students feel prepared to perform in global contexts? These are examples of emergent questions to investigate further, taking both qualitative and quantitative methods and in diverse parts of world and learning environments. By doing so, engineering education research

has the knowledge and tools to become proactive towards societal changes rather than reactive.

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